

Rapid sensors connected in an Internet-of-Things environment: the case of agriculture

BioSense's Group for Nano and Microelectronics is concerned with development of various sensors for agriculture which aim to characterise soil conditions in which plants grow and detect stress. Plant-O-Meter is a visual sensor that operates in 4 spectral bands that were found to be indicative of water and nutrient deficiency. It measures the ratio of emitted and reflected light and gives 16 different vegetation indices. Its biggest advantage is that it is connected to mobile phone via Bluetooth, so that the processing of readings is done on mobile phone's CPU, effectively lowering the price of manufacturing. Next two sensors are dedicated to frequent, fast and reliable measurement and mapping of nitrogen and nitrates in the soil. The first one is an optical device which is based on a colorimetric method. Soil solution sample is mixed with nitrogen-reactive nanoparticles, which obtain different colour intensity depending on the total concentration of nitrogen in the sample. Colorimetric spectrophotometer then measures the absorption of light in the sample which indicates the nitrogen concentration. As for the second sensor, it is an ion-selective electrode immersed in the soil solution that gives the value of the concentration of nitrates, which is then read by an Arduino-based device. Extreme weather conditions such as drought or excessive humidity are the trigger for aflatoxin expansion in maize. Aflatoxin is a dangerous mycotoxin which is proven to have a negative effect on human and animal health. It is triggered by extreme weather conditions, such as drought and excessive humidity. Here, we propose a fast, low-cost method for pre-harvest monitoring and pinpoint the aflatoxin concentration in maize. It is an optical method based on fluorescence of contaminated ears excited by UV radiation and it can be used for detection of highly contaminated ears (< 1M ppb).

In order to integrate sensory data, we designed AgroSense – the official platform of Digital Agriculture of Serbia. This platform is free and user-friendly and helps farmers plan and document their activities more efficiently, which is why more than 10,000 of them are actively using it. In the process of registration, the user chooses his parcels from the cadastre and momentarily, he is given the localised weather forecast, historical meteo records, satellite vegetation indices and other data. There is also a module for keeping a digital diary of the production. The farmer can choose crops and varieties planted and fertilisers and pesticides applied from a drop-down menu of varieties and agro-chemicals registered in Serbia and get cost analysis. Another module is concerned with plant diseases. Extension services are monitoring crops on a daily level and teams are sent to fields across Serbia. In the case of occurrence of plant diseases, information about the name of the disease and type of crop affected is sent to AgroSense and all farmers from the area who are cultivating that crop are alerted and can quickly act.

When it comes to crop monitoring, AgroSense relies on LoRa (long-range and low-power technology) for communicating with field sensors. Measurements are stored in the database and instantly shown on the platform, so that the farmer can instantly make decisions. A new module currently being developed is concerned with smart irrigation. First, machine learning model was trained to predicted soil moisture based on the amount of rainfall and length of irrigation. This AgroSense module relies on the machine learning model to estimates the optimal amount of irrigation based on the current sensory readings and weather forecast for the next 5 days. In this way, the consumption of resources is minimised, making the production more efficient and eco-friendly.